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The Portrayal of Tradition and Modernity in Ousmane Sembène's *Xala*

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Abstract:

Ousmane Sembène in *Xala* portrays the intersection of tradition and modernity in postcolonial Senegal. His works point out the issues which the African society faced due to colonialism, and *Xala* is no exception. Western modernity was regarded as superior and African tradition as inferior by colonizers. People started adopting a Western lifestyle to appear superior and civilized. Sembène highlights some issues such as loss of language, customs, and cultural identity, which were the impact of the long term colonial rule, leaving a lasting mark in postcolonial Senegalese society. Furthermore, this paper analyzes the clash between tradition and modernity through various instances by examining the shift in power from colonizers, who distorted the image of indigenous people or traditional communities to bourgeoisies, taking their place after independence. This paper will explore how Sembène critiques this transformation and exposes the internalized colonial legacy within the postcolonial elite.

Keywords: Tradition, Modernity, Language, Lifestyle, Postcolonialism, Africa.

INTRODUCTION

Africa being the second largest crowded mainland with an immense amount of resources was colonized by European forces in the 1880s. Colonizers viewed their culture as superior, imposing their language, education, and customs on colonized nations; their actions were meant to erode the culture and tradition of Africans. They treated their subjects as “savages” who needed to be civilized. They justified their acts by associating Africans with the Noah’s

curse, calling them the descendants of Ham, further, making them believe that they were the inferior race and to become civilized and superior like colonizers they had to adopt their culture. Thus, the African culture and tradition were exploited and suffered heavily under the colonialist rule, further eroding the rituals and beliefs of the indigenous people or community.

Moreover, this paper deals with the issue of Western modernity and its impact on tradition in the novel *Xala* (1976) by Ousmane Sembène. Tradition involves stories or customs which were passed down from one generation to another for the preservation of the beliefs and customs of their society. It was mainly related to the ancient way of life. On the other hand, modernity refers to the new way of life not experienced earlier. Modernity includes various elements, which go hand in hand in the colonization process like capitalism, social stratification, technology, innovation, and westernization. Westernization played a significant role in the colonization process of various countries. Through westernization colonizers upheld their customs as superior to their subjects'. Furthermore, modernity seems beneficial for some but disadvantageous for many. This is evident in the case of natives who were considered as 'other' by newly rich bourgeoisies.

Additionally, be it in East Africa or West Africa, people tend to share a worldview that tradition was related to African nations or other colonized nations while modernity was related to colonisers. This created a barrier between the two. The native people began questioning their identity, values, and beliefs. Earlier people were not involved and did not know much about tradition and modernity binary. However, due to this binary creation people began to avoid their traditional practices and turned to adopting the lifestyle of the West. They conform to the colonizers standard of superiority. Colonizers made a childlike image of Africans who needed guidance to get stability or for development purposes.

Furthermore, people were anxious and hopeful for the new kinds of articulations post-independence. However, things did not change much. Their happiness lasted only for a

short period of time. After the coloniser's rule the African Bourgeoisie's assumed their position. This indicates that it was just the change of drivers and not the change in direction. The transition from tradition to modern ways left an impression on the indigenous community, which somehow proved helpful to colonizers, facilitating them to achieve their goal. These changes led to the rise of writers who wrote about their African culture and communal practices, which worked as the step towards safeguarding their identity, practices, and beliefs. Their works were indicative of the impacts of colonialism. Further, showcasing the journey from tradition to modernity and Western way of living.

The Beginnings

Ousmane Sembène is the writer and filmmaker, titled as the father of African films. His works revolve around the political and historical themes of post-independence Senegal. He wrote his novel *Xala* (1976) as a satire on modern day bourgeoisies. The story takes place in Dakar, the capital of Senegal in West Africa. It came under the rule of the French empire in the 17th century, implying direct rule on the local population, afterwards it became a complete colonization in the 19th century. The French empire started trading at the bay in Senegal, exploiting their colonies by trading gold, acacia gum, and enslaved people; furthermore, dehumanizing their labour force. People under French colonial rule were able to free themselves in the 1960s.

Moreover, Sembène through the protagonist El Hadji Abdu Haider Beye shows the fall of a bourgeoisie from the position of an important person to the most humiliated man as a result of the curse of impotence. Impotence was caused due to a curse from the beggar who reveals himself at the end of the story, he is the one whom El Hadji once cheated. The cure of the impotence was El Hadji should stand naked and the beggars will spit on him. El Hadji accepts to get cure from the beggars in desperation to get free from the curse of impotence. Sembène

portrayed through his protagonist how people who resist their tradition, identity, and customs get back to it in the cruellest way possible.

The colonizers upheld their standard of superiority, which resulted in the acceptance of western modernity by the African intellectuals who distanced themselves from their tradition. They conform to colonial modernity to help their nation in the development process. However, instead of helping the native people these intellectuals took their rights. It is evident that El Hadji, the capitalist businessman, who chose Western modernity to help the local population rather used it for his own benefit. Earlier he used to be a;

Primary-school teacher, but he had been dismissed from the service because of his involvement in trade-union activity during the colonial period. After his dismissal he had acquired business experience in the grocery trade and had then set himself up as a middleman in property transactions. (9)

El Hadji in the pursuit of a modern lifestyle cheated on the people of his nation. This transformation is like Chui in *Petals of Blood* (1977) by Ngugi Wa Thiong'o. He also strives for a modern lifestyle and in this process he cheated on the natives by indulging in capitalist practices. Further, traditional practices were labelled as parochial and old fashioned. The shift from tradition to modernity eroded a part of their identity, which was language.

Language which plays a significant role in forming one's cultural identity was denied by modern bourgeoisie like El Hadji and other elites who chose French, the language of power and eliteness, over their language 'Wolof'. They were proud and delighted to use the language of colonizers. El Hadji preferred to speak in French and so did his wife Oumi N'Doye. Further, Rama speaks Wolof which is not appreciated by her father El Hadji. There is an instance in the novel where the policeman is speaking French, a state-controlled institution. He says,

A policeman advanced on them. Very politely, he asked in French: ‘Your driving licence please, madam.’ Rama glanced at Pathé, turned, all feminine, to the policeman and said in Wolof: ‘My brother, excuse me, I cannot understand what you are saying.’ (50)

The policeman replies to her and says,

‘You don’t understand French?’ he asked in Wolof. ‘I don’t understand French, my brother.’ ‘How did you get your driving licence then?’ (50)

These instances are indicative of how these state-controlled institutions were still following the policies of colonizers. The language gave colonisers the power to control their colonized subjects and to exploit their subjects' identity, tradition, and uniqueness. In pursuit of power and to get a ticket to western civilized society, these newly rich bourgeoisies abandoned their language. Nevertheless, people who fought for their country used their language ‘Wolof’ as a weapon to rebel and resist the colonisers' rule and to get independence. During colonial rule, language politics was related to the question of loyalty and nationalism; allegiance to a nation was decided on the basis of the language they chose for themselves. After independence the elites resisted their tradition, identity, and beliefs by abandoning their language.

Furthermore, El Hadji wore a European suit which was not a suitable dress according to the weather of Africa. However, his first wife Adja Awa Astou wore a traditional dress (Boubou), indicative of following a traditional lifestyle. His second wife “Oumi N’Doye saw El Hadji in her mirror. She was securing her black wig with the aid of pins”. (Sembene,21) Wearing a wig and dressing in European fashion shows the will to follow the modern lifestyle and to become a part of the Western culture. Wearing wigs was not a part of African culture, but black women started following the fashion of white women. Before wigs came into trend,

black women used to iron their hair and cream it just like white women. Furthermore, Lawino comments in "Song of Lawino"(1966) by Okot p'Bitek:

They cook their hair
with hot iron
and pull it hard
so that it may grow long (37)

Lawino is talking about African women who used to straighten their hair to look like white women, a way of losing a part of their identity. OumiN'Doye aspires to look like white women because it is a web woven by Western society which still works in contemporary times, as Lawino comments,

brother when you see clementine
the beautiful one aspires
to look like a white woman (54)

During colonization, Eurocentric standards of aesthetics devalued African beauty and viewed Western beauty as inherently superior. Beauty standards set by the Western world contributed to the exploitation and marginalization of other ethnic groups. For them, beauty means white skin with straight blonde hair and blue eyes. In *The Bluest Eye* (1970) by Toni Morrison, the narrator says,

It had occurred to Pecola some time ago that if her eyes, those eyes that held the pictures, and knew the sights—if those eyes of hers were different, that is to say, beautiful, she herself would be different. (38)

Pecola also desires to have blue eyes to look beautiful and different, which is associated with white skin, creating a sense of inferiority complex in the colonial subjects.

Moreover, in the novel, the house of Oumi N'Doye was set in the style of modern French custom. The narrator says,

Oumi N'Doye had prepared her aye in a spirit of rivalry. A reunion meal. The menu culled from a French fashion magazine. She wanted to make him forget the last meal he had with his first wife. The table was laid in the French way. There were various hors d'œuvres and veal cutlets. The Côtes de Provence rose kept the bottle of French mineral water company in the ice-bucket; at the other end of the table a pyramid of apples and pears. (58)

The eagerness of the bourgeoisies to adopt French ideals in their lifestyle to look modern and appealing. Oumi N'Doye used French table etiquettes and brands, which were reflective of the cultural transition that people experienced in post-independence Africa. During this process, people were confused about their identity, resulting in the erosion of traditional customs. Through various instances in the novel it is evident that Oumi N'Doye was reduced to an object of desire by El Hadji. However, El Hadji and his wife Oumi N'Doye in an effort to embrace a modern way of living rejected their traditional values and customs, labelling them old fashioned. This is evident from an instance in the novel, where El Hadji was asked by Yay Bineta to sit on a mortar with a pestle before his wedding night with N'Gone, his third wife. The custom of sitting on a mortar was used as a traditional cleansing ritual to overcome the spell of impotence. Yay Bineta asks him,

You must put on a caftan without trousers and sit there on the mortar, with the axe-handle held between your feet, until your wife's arrival is announced. Yay Bineta, you don't really believe in all that! I have two wives already and I did not make a fool of myself with this hocus-pocus on their account. And I am not going to start today! (24)

El Hadji did not perform this ritual as it made no sense to him. Colonized subjects' values and customs were labelled as irrational and meaningless by colonizers and then by elites. These instances made people lose confidence in their values and traditions. Thus, making them question their way of living compared to that of the colonizers. Tradition played a significant role in the formation of the identity of diverse indigenous groups. However, colonial subjects still avoided their tradition and followed the path of Western modernity. Furthermore, their skin colour was not the gateway to the modern, cosmopolitan, and civilized world. As a result, they chose to pursue the language, customs and lifestyle of colonizers.

Sembène through the character of El Hadji portrayed the mindset of newly rich bourgeoisies who first denied all their customs and traditions. Nevertheless, they followed the traditional practices only to get some benefit in society. He got the title of 'El Hadji' because he made a pilgrimage to Mecca. However, he is not religious, which is evident through various instances in the novel. Pilgrimage was made to enhance his status in front of the members of his business group. His prosperity was won by theft and lacks the quality of a pilgrim who helps people in need. Also, he is one of those people whose material life is built on the sufferings of the poor.

In a race towards the modern way of living people like El Hadji chose material possessions which were temporary. He tried finding happiness in his materialistic lifestyle and from his delusional identity, denying his traditional roots. However, he was not able to find it. The material wealth which he owns is evident in the novel from his three villas, which he gave to his wife. Other than villas he owns cars and a mini bus for his children. He made villas in the Porsche areas where people of importance live, far away from the reality of life. The reality of life reminds him of his past and identity, which he does not want to recall. Villas are representative of his social status and wealth. However, villas do not give him a sense of

security or a feel of home. He runs from one wife's villa to the other in his Mercedes which provides him a temporary shelter.

Moreover, in the novel, El Hadji was wandering around to find the cure of *Xala*. He travels to the village of Sereen Mada, where he has to change his Mercedes to a horse cart for travelling into the world of Serren Mada. In the village of Sereen Mada he felt alienated due to the shift from urban to rural and from modern to traditional ways. To get cure of *Xala* 'a man of honour' was lying naked in front of an ordinary villager. The spells, cures, and potions were the powerful tools of non-Westernised people. Sereen Mada cured him temporarily to make him conscious of his identity. However, as soon as he returned to his urban life and modern ways, the curse of *Xala* was restored back. The permanent cure of the impotence was with the beggar who caused him *Xala*, and he asks El Hadji :

If you want to be cured, you are going to strip yourself naked, completely naked, El Hadji. Naked before us all. And each of us will spit three times on you. You have the key to your cure. Make up your mind. I can tell you now, it was I who caused your *Xala*. (111)

The curse symbolizes the anger of the indigenous people who were exploited firstly by the hands of colonizers and then by the people of their nation in pursuit of wealth, power, and Western modernity. Furthermore, it led to the erosion of tradition, language, and beliefs.

Conclusion

Sembène satirizes the shift from tradition to modernity through the character of El Hadji, a capitalistic, French speaking businessman who built his empire on the sufferings of the natives. The indigenous people were representative of traditional beliefs and practices, however, bourgeoisie's like El Hadji were representative of Western colonial modernity who

wanted to fit in the standards set by the colonizers to gain power and wealth. Their capitalist mindset and Western practices led to the depletion of traditional values and identity. Like African countries, other nations who were once colonized also lost their heritage of traditions. Sembene through his works portrayed the journey of El Hadji who chose to resist his tradition and identity, however, he returned to it to get free from the curse of *Xala*.

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